

Cueing-assisted gamified augmented-reality home rehabilitation for gait and balance in people with Parkinson's disease: feasibility and effectiveness in the clinical pathway

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Abstract

Objective: This trial evaluated the clinical feasibility and potential effectiveness of Strolll, an augmented reality (AR) neurorehabilitation platform offering gamified gait-and-balance exercises complemented with assistive AR cueing for individuals with Parkinson's disease, implemented in real-world clinical practice. Additionally, we assessed how to tailor AR cues to assist gait during AR exercises.

Methods: In this pragmatic clinical trial, we onboarded 15 clinics in the Netherlands, trained 28 therapists, and included 100 individuals with Parkinson's disease (Hoehn and Yahr stages 1-3). All participants followed the T0-usual-care-control-T1-Strolll-intervention-T2 procedure. The Strolll intervention consisted of a two-week supervised in-clinic training followed by 6 weeks, 5 sessions/week, 30 active minutes, independent home-based training.

Results: No serious adverse events occurred; only two non-injurious falls were reported in >60.000 performed exercise minutes. Adherence was high (96% session adherence and 91% active minutes/session adherence). Therapists prescribed the program progressively, with significantly higher game-play levels over time. Participants' performance on exercises increased over time. Participants and therapists rated user experience and technology acceptance positively. Significant improvements in Timed-Up-and-Go and 10-Meter Walk Test (fast speed) scores occurred after the intervention period

30 only. Five-Times Sit-to-Stand, 10-Meter Walk Test (comfortable speed), and Mini Balance Evaluation
31 Systems Test scores improved after both usual-care and intervention periods. Falls Efficacy Scale
32 International scores showed no significant improvements. AR cueing was deemed beneficial for a subset
33 of participants.

34 **Conclusion:** Stroll is a safe, adherable, progressive, usable, and well-accepted therapist-managed, home-
35 based intervention for people with Parkinson's disease, with the potential to improve gait, balance, and
36 fall-risk indicators. Findings on the integration of AR cueing highlight the importance of an
37 individualized approach.

38 **Impact:** Implementing AR rehabilitation technologies like Stroll in the clinical pathway is feasible,
39 offering a safe and scalable way for individuals to train independently, potentially improving accessibility
40 of care and broadening its use to physical activity promotion.

41 **Trial registration**

42 ClinicalTrials.gov: NCT06590987

43

44 **Keywords (3-10):** Parkinson's disease, augmented reality, cueing, gait, balance, rehabilitation, gamified
45 exercise, clinical practice, telerehabilitation, blended-care

46

1. Background

Parkinson's disease is the fastest-growing, progressive neurological disease with a severe impact on the healthcare system¹. Gait-and-balance impairments are common in people with Parkinson's disease, contributing to an increased risk of falls and a reduced quality of life². Exercise and physiotherapy are considered essential for people with Parkinson's disease to maintain and improve motor function, decelerate further decline, and promote overall health and well-being^{3,4}. Nevertheless, due to mobility impairments and other practical limitations, individuals with Parkinson's disease often face challenges attending to regular, center-based rehabilitation programs over a prolonged period⁵, while adherence rates to prescribed exercise at home are typically low⁶. Various home-based rehabilitation interventions have emerged for maintaining and enhancing motor function and achieving overall health benefits^{7,8}. Despite their potential, traditional home-based exercise interventions often suffer from low therapy adherence and limited monitoring capabilities for therapists⁹. Emerging technologies with gamified exercises and captured exercise data offer promising and engaging solutions to these limitations¹⁰.

Augmented reality (AR) glasses, such as Magic Leap 2 or Microsoft HoloLens 2, represent a promising innovation in this domain, allowing for an interactive experience within an individual's environment. This technology is embodied in the development of Strolll, an AR neurorehabilitation platform with gamified gait-and-balance exercises specifically designed for people with Parkinson's disease for use in the clinic or at home (see Figure 1A-F, H-I and Supplementary Video 1), which can be managed by therapists for supervised in-clinic therapy as well as for asynchronous telerehabilitation independently at home¹¹. A recent controlled feasibility study in a science-led setting demonstrated that the earlier version of Strolll (previously called Reality DTx®) is safe, usable, adherable, and well-accepted for independent use at home, with targeted intervention effects for improving gait, balance, and fall risk in people with Parkinson's disease¹². A key innovation of the Strolll platform is the integration of AR cueing, involving visual or auditory stimuli to assist and modify gait during the gamified exercises¹³. These AR cues may be used by individuals with more severe gait impairments, like freezing of gait and

72 festination, to assist them with AR exercises that require walking and turning. Since cueing is not a one-
73 size-fits-all solution¹⁴⁻¹⁶, these AR cues are probably most beneficial when tailored to the individual (i.e.,
74 type of cue and settings).

75 This pragmatic clinical trial is designed to investigate the clinical feasibility and potential
76 effectiveness of Stroll implemented in real-world clinical practice. We expected that Stroll is i) clinically
77 feasible in terms of safety, adherence, performance, user experience, and acceptability (for individuals
78 with Parkinson's disease and their therapists) and ii) potentially effective for improving gait, balance, and
79 fall-risk indicators. Additionally, we evaluated procedures to i) identify participants deemed to benefit
80 from complementary AR cues in AR exercises and ii) individually tailor AR cue characteristics. We
81 expected that a subset of participants, particularly those with severe mobility impairments such as
82 freezing of gait and festination, could benefit from adding complementary AR cues and that the selected
83 type of cue and its settings varied over participants (i.e., cueing is not a one-size-fits-all solution^{15,16}).

84

85 **Figure 1** Stroll gait-and-balance exercises (A-F, H-I) implemented in the clinical pathway in the
 86 Netherlands (G). Specific exercises were Smash! (without [A] and with [B] assistive AR cues), Mole
 87 Patroo (C), Puzzle Walk (D), Cue Challenge (E), Basketball (F), Wobbly Waiter (H), and Hot Buttons
 88 (I).

89 2. Methods

90 The trial was registered on Clinicaltrials.gov (NCT06590987). The methods are concisely described here,
 91 with a fully detailed study protocol previously published¹⁷. Deviations from the published study protocol
 92 (i.e., required adjustment of the statistical analysis¹⁸) are documented and justified in the Transparent
 93 Changes document (Supplementary Material 1).

94 **2.1 Study setting, design, and procedures**

95 This study was implemented in the clinical pathway at 15 healthcare practices affiliated with
96 ParkinsonNet, Dutch society for Parkinson's therapists¹⁹, across the Netherlands (Figure 1G): Pieter van
97 Foreest, Houding & Bewegen, Verheul & Weerman Fysiotherapeuten, BeweegBewust, PACA, Motion
98 Fysiotherapie & Preventie, SFR Beweegt, Fysiotherapie Zwaansvliet, Careyn, Norschoten, Parkinson
99 TrainingsCentrum, Kr8, Leidsche Rijn Julius Gezondheidscentra, Fysiotherapeuten Maatschap Woerden
100 and Parkinson Centraal. All therapists involved (n=28) were trained in using Strolll and familiarized with
101 the study procedure, including administering the clinical assessments¹⁷.

102 This pragmatic clinical trial included three in-clinic assessments performed by the participant's
103 therapist, which we aimed to schedule at the same time of day to minimize the influence of medication
104 and ON/OFF motor fluctuations. After the baseline assessment (T0), participants underwent a 6-week
105 usual-care period, followed by a pre-intervention assessment (T1). During the usual-care period,
106 participants received no additional instructions or therapy related to Strolll and continued their regular
107 weekly therapy schedule, generally consisting of in-clinic sessions adhering to physiotherapy guidelines
108 for Parkinson's disease^{3,4}, possibly supplemented by prescribed conventional home exercises (e.g., paper-
109 listed or video clips demonstrating the exercises). This was followed by two weeks of supervised in-clinic
110 training with Strolll, after which participants used Strolll independently at home for 6 weeks,
111 asynchronously managed by their therapists, and integrated with their regular in-clinic usual-care
112 sessions. Participants finished the study with a post-intervention assessment (T2). This design, where all
113 participants followed the same T0-control-T1-intervention-T2 procedure, streamlined implementation in a
114 real-world clinical setting and facilitated the assessment of both clinical feasibility and potential
115 effectiveness.

116 **2.2 Study population**

117 Participants (N=100, based on an a-priori power analysis¹⁷) were recruited by their physiotherapist or
118 exercise therapist in the participating healthcare practices. Eligibility was established through telephone

119 screening by the researchers. Participants were included if they had been diagnosed with Parkinson's
120 disease (stages 1-3 on the Hoehn and Yahr scale), experienced self-reported gait and/or balance
121 impairments, were aged 21 years or over, and proficient in the Dutch language. Exclusion criteria
122 included neurological and/or orthopedic conditions seriously affecting gait, severe cognitive, visual,
123 and/or hearing impairments (after corrective aids), insufficient physical capacity (e.g., frequent faller
124 and/or the inability to walk independently for 30 minutes), severe visual hallucinations and/or illusions,
125 and unstable dosage of medication at the start of the study. All participants provided written informed
126 consent before participating in the study.

127 **2.3 Intervention**

128 The Strolll intervention, a certified neurorehabilitation software platform developed for AR glasses in
129 collaboration with Strolll Limited (www.strolll.co), was delivered in two stages. In the first stage,
130 therapists introduced participants to Strolll during a two-week supervised in-clinic training period,
131 allowing participants to familiarize themselves with the technology and evaluate the potential benefits of
132 AR cueing. Strolll comprises seven complementary gamified exercises: Mole Patrolll, Smash!,
133 Basketballl, Hot Buttons, Puzzle Walk, Wobbly Waiter, and Cue Challenge, delivered via state-of-the-art
134 AR glasses (i.e., HoloLens 2 and Magic Leap 2), see Figure 1A-F,H-I and Supplementary Video 1, each
135 designed to improve aspects of gait, balance, and fall risk. AR cues could be added to Smash! and Cue
136 Challenge (Supplementary Video 2) to support or improve the participant's gait (e.g., increasing step
137 length, alleviating freezing). During the in-clinic training period, all types of cues were explored
138 (Supplementary Material 2) and tailored to the participant by their therapist (e.g., step length, step height,
139 color). When deemed beneficial, the most suitable AR cue was selected through a shared decision-making
140 process involving the participant and therapist during the in-clinic training period and added to Smash!
141 and Cue Challenge. The other walking-based exercises, Mole Patrolll, Puzzle Walk, and Wobbly Waiter,
142 already incorporated AR-mediated goal-directed elements acting as spatial location cues (moles, puzzle
143 pieces) or spatiotemporal cues (moving waiter). A detailed description of the gamified exercises and cues
144 can be found in Supplementary Material 2. At the end of the in-clinic period, therapists, in consultation

145 with the participant, decided whether the Strolll intervention at home was deemed safe and suitable for
146 the participants; if not, participants discontinued the study. The second stage comprised six weeks of
147 training with Strolll independently at home, consisting of 30-minute sessions five days per week by
148 default, following the recommended 150 exercise minutes per week²⁰, with adjustments based on
149 individual capacity as determined by the therapist. The therapists were instructed to remotely prescribe,
150 evaluate, and adjust the exercise program weekly, with the option to modify each gamified exercise
151 separately in terms of duration, level, and settings, through the Strolll web portal. By default, all exercises
152 were prescribed for each participant, although therapists could adjust the selection if needed. This process
153 was guided by shared decision-making between participant and therapist using participant's feedback and
154 therapist's clinical expertise, and potentially driven by adherence and game scores (e.g., number of moles
155 spawned, meters walked; see Supplementary Material 2) from the Strolll web portal as input.

156 **2.4 Outcomes**

157 The clinical feasibility of Strolll was assessed in terms of safety (i.e., adverse events while using Strolll,
158 such as falls or dizziness, and weekly fall rate in daily life), adherence (i.e., adherence to the prescribed
159 number of sessions and the prescribed active minutes/session), performance (i.e., game-related and
160 functional performance scores), user experience, and acceptability. User experience and acceptability
161 were evaluated using the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ)^{21,22}, a technology acceptance and use
162 questionnaire (based on the model of Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology²³), a top-3
163 advantages and disadvantages of Strolll for future clinical implementation, and a Strolll intervention-
164 specific questionnaire including items on the integration of AR cues. Additionally, therapists' experiences
165 were assessed with comparable questionnaires, followed by a post-study process evaluation in focus
166 groups, which will be reported in a separate qualitative paper. A final feasibility outcome was the
167 proportion of participants deemed eligible for training independently at home and the number of
168 intervention-related dropouts.

169 Standardized clinical gait-and-balance assessments, which are indicators of fall risk²⁴⁻²⁷, were
170 administered to evaluate the potential effectiveness of the intervention at baseline, pre-, and post-
171 intervention (T0, T1, T2). The Timed Up-and-Go test (TUG) was the primary outcome used for the
172 sample-size calculation, with as secondary outcomes the Five Times Sit-to-Stand test (FTSTS), 10-Meter
173 Walk Test at comfortable and fast speeds (10MWT), Mini Balance Evaluation Scale Test (Mini-
174 BESTest), and Falls Efficacy Scale International (FES-I).

175 To evaluate the integration of AR cues within the gamified exercises, we documented whether
176 participants used AR cues during the Stroll intervention, along with the specific type of AR cue, its
177 settings (e.g., length, height, width), and the rationale for using the AR cue (e.g., alleviating freezing of
178 gait or increasing step length).

179 **2.5 Statistical analysis**

180 Safety was described by the number of adverse events, including a paired-samples *t*-test comparison of
181 the average weekly number of falls experienced during the usual-care and intervention periods.

182 Adherence to the Stroll intervention was assessed with a repeated-measures ANOVA with the within-
183 subject factor Time (three levels: first, second, and third part, so approximately two-week intervals, of
184 Stroll intervention at home). In case of significant main effects of Time, post-hoc paired-samples *t*-tests
185 were conducted, with Bonferroni-adjusted *p*-values. With one-sample *t*-tests against 100%, we evaluated
186 possible systematic deviations in adherence from what was prescribed. To assess whether Stroll
187 integrated into the clinical pathway was prescribed in a progressive yet achievable manner, we subjected
188 game levels and performance scores (see Supplementary Material 2) to repeated-measures ANOVAs or
189 their non-parametric equivalents with Time as a within-subject factor (three levels: first, second, and third
190 part), using paired-samples *t*-tests (or non-parametric equivalents) for post-hoc analyses of significant
191 main effects, with *p*-values adjusted using the Bonferroni correction. Since analyses were conducted
192 independently for each gamified exercise, we did not apply an additional correction for multiple exercises
193 beyond the within-analysis adjustments. The UEQ outcomes were described descriptively and interpreted

194 against known benchmark scores²². All other user experience and acceptability outcomes were processed
195 descriptively, for both participants and therapists.

196 The potential effectiveness of Strolll on clinical gait-and-balance test outcomes was evaluated
197 using a linear mixed-effects (LME) model with Time (T0, T1, T2) as a fixed effect and Participant as a
198 random intercept. Contrast testing with the first (T1-T0) and second (T2-mean(T1, T0)) reverse Helmert
199 contrasts was done to evaluate potential control and intervention effects, respectively. For transparency,
200 we note that this effectiveness analysis deviated from the previously published study protocol¹⁷, as
201 justified in the Transparent Changes document (Supplementary Material 1). Results of the pre-planned
202 repeated-measures ANOVAs (within-subjects comparisons) were comparable with the results of the LME
203 analyses (as detailed in Supplementary Material 9).

204 All statistical analyses were performed in JASP²⁸ with significance set at $\alpha=0.05$. Missing data of
205 feasibility outcomes were excluded analysis-by-analysis. For three participants, one or two missing items
206 on the Mini-BESTest were imputed. For all repeated-measures ANOVAs, the Huynh-Feldt correction was
207 applied if Greenhouse–Geisser’s epsilon exceeded 0.750, otherwise, the Greenhouse–Geisser correction
208 was used. Effect sizes were quantified as η_p^2 .

209 **3. Results**

210 **3.1 Participants**

211 Participants were recruited between May and October 2024. Out of 132 recruited people with Parkinson’s
212 disease assessed for eligibility, 100 enrolled in the study. These 100 participants had a mean age of
213 69.6 ± 8.2 years (range 42-87 years; 72 males, 28 females) and Hoehn & Yahr stages 1 (N=26), 2 (N=53),
214 and 3 (N=21), with 37 participants qualifying as freezers (defined by a non-zero score on the New
215 Freezing Of Gait Questionnaire²⁹). A detailed overview of participant flow and characteristics is provided
216 in Supplementary Material 3 and 4, respectively. After the supervised in-clinic sessions, six of the 98
217 remaining participants did not continue with home-based training: one experienced excessive discomfort

218 with the AR glasses, two were unwilling to take Strolll home, two had insufficient cognitive capacity, and
219 one had insufficient physical capacity. The remaining 92 participants (93.9%) took the AR glasses home
220 for independent use. Among the 92 participants, there were 14 dropouts, five of which were unrelated to
221 the intervention, resulting in a dropout rate of 15%. Between July 2024 and February 2025, 78 out of 92
222 participants completed the 6-week home training with Strolll. For five participants, the final clinical
223 assessment (T2) is missing due to personal circumstances, resulting in 73 participants who completed the
224 T2 clinical assessment. Dropouts were included where available in both the feasibility and effectiveness
225 analysis, resulting in a sample of up to 92 participants (see Supplementary Material 3).

226 **3.2 Clinical feasibility**

227 *3.2.1 Safety*

228 There were no serious adverse events. Two non-injurious falls were reported while using the Strolll
229 platform, one supervised in-clinic and one independently at home. The average weekly fall rate in daily
230 life did not differ significantly between usual-care and intervention periods ($Z=-0.02$, $p=0.991$). Twelve
231 participants experienced dizziness at least once, four reported headaches, and fifteen reported eyestrain
232 (for a comprehensive overview, see Supplementary Material 5). In the Strolll evaluation questionnaire,
233 participants generally reported feeling safe and did not express fear of falling while training at home with
234 Strolll. Five participants disagreed with feeling safe, two of whom dropped out.

235 *3.2.2 Adherence*

236 Participants who completed the 6-week Strolll home training ($N=78$) performed an average of 731
237 minutes ($SD=255$) of active exercise. Session adherence was high, on average 96% (Figure 2A), but
238 decreased slightly over Time ($F(2,154)=5.10$, $p=0.007$, $\eta_p^2=0.062$), with a significant post-hoc difference
239 between the means of the first and third parts of the intervention period ($M=99.67\%$, $SD=25.87$ vs.
240 $M=91.38\%$, $SD=23.35$; $t(77)=3.00$, $p=0.011$, for which the third part deviated significantly from 100%
241 ($Z=864.50$, $p=0.008$)). Active minutes/session adherence was 91% (Figure 2B) and did not differ over

242 Time ($F(1.439,110.795)=1.69, p=0.196, \eta_p^2=0.021$), although it significantly deviated from 100% (all
 243 $Z>270.50, p<0.001$).

244
 245 **Figure 2.** Session adherence (A) and active minutes/session adherence (B) for the first (I), second (II),
 246 and third (III) part of the Stroll intervention period at home, with the dots representing individual
 247 participants. Error bars represent the standard error of the mean. Asterisks indicate significant post-hoc
 248 differences over Time or deviations from 100% (* $p<0.05$ and ** $p<0.001$).

249
 250 *3.2.3 Game-play level and performance*

251 The Stroll intervention was prescribed in a progressive manner, with game-play levels significantly
 252 increasing over Time for all gamified exercises ($\chi^2(2)>29.94, p<0.001$), showing significant post-hoc
 253 differences between all three intervention time points ($t>2.84, p<0.05$; see Figure 3A). Both game-play
 254 performance scores (e.g., the number of moles wacked per minute) and functional performance scores
 255 (e.g., meters walked per minute) improved significantly over Time for Mole Patrol, Puzzle Walk and
 256 Wobbly Waiter (game-play scores: all $F>10.27, p<0.001, \eta_p^2>0.119$; functional scores: all $F>14.81,$
 257 $p<0.001, \eta_p^2>0.252$, see Figure 3). For Smash!, the significant decline in the game-play performance
 258 score (fewer rounds per minute; $F(1.374,105.797)=9.76, p<0.001, \eta_p^2=0.113$) was accompanied by an
 259 increase in the functional performance score (more functional reaches per minute;
 260 $F(1.304,100.405)=85.32, p<0.001, \eta_p^2=0.526$). For Basketball, the game-play performance score (rounds

261 per minute) did not change over Time ($F(1.333,97.277)=1.32, p=0.264, \eta_p^2=0.018$), whereas the
262 functional performance score (number of squats or sit-to-stands per minute) increased significantly over
263 Time ($F(1.220,89.046)=52.04, p<0.001, \eta_p^2=0.416$). These deviating findings for Smash! and Basketball
264 followed directly from particular gamified-exercise mechanics, where higher game-play levels required
265 substantially more functional reaches or squats/sit-to-stands to complete a round. In Hot Buttons, the
266 game-play performance score (correctly pressed buttons per minute) improved significantly over Time
267 ($F(1.764,135.859)=10.29, p<0.001, \eta_p^2=0.118$) while the functional performance score (number of
268 functional reaches per minute) did not vary over time ($F(1.635,125.926)=1.69, p=0.198, \eta_p^2=0.021$).
269 Figure 3 ranks the gamified exercises by frequency of play. Since Cue Challenge was the least prescribed
270 exercise, performed consistently over time by only 15 participants, associated performance scores were
271 not analyzed.

Performance

■ Game-play performance ■ Functional performance

273 **Figure 3.** Game-play level (A), game-play performance scores (dark blue) and functional performance
274 scores (light blue)(B-G) of gamified exercises for the first (I), second (II), and third (II) part of the Strolll
275 intervention, ranked by frequency of play. Error bars represent the standard error of the mean. Asterisks
276 indicate a significant main effect of Time (** $p < 0.001$).

277 3.2.4 User experience and technology acceptance

278 The user experience and acceptance of the Strolll intervention were overall positive for both participants
279 and therapists (Figures 4 and 5). All UEQ subscales were rated between ‘above average’ and ‘excellent’
280 relative to UEQ benchmarks²², except for the ‘efficiency’ subscale, which therapists rated ‘below
281 average’ (Figure 4B). Figure 5 shows the distribution of scores for the Likert-scale (1-5) questions of the
282 Strolll evaluation questionnaire and the technology acceptance questionnaire. Across all subscales of the
283 technology acceptance questionnaire, scores were generally positively rated, similarly for participants and
284 therapists (Figure 5). That is, participants/therapists: 1) expected to/expected their patients to benefit from
285 the intervention (perceived expectancy; participants: $M=3.90$, $SD=0.63$; therapists: $M=4.15$, $SD=0.69$), 2)
286 experienced the technology to be easy to use (effort expectancy; participants: $M=4.08$, $SD=0.58$;
287 therapists: $M=3.95$, $SD=0.71$) and 3) felt that significant others believe that the technology should be used
288 (social influence; participants: $M=3.77$, $SD=0.63$; therapists: $M=3.52$, $SD=0.89$). The subscale
289 ‘facilitating conditions’ cannot be interpreted because of a low internal consistency for the participants
290 (Cronbach’s $\alpha=0.37$) and should therefore be considered at item level (see Figure 5). Finally, there was a
291 positive behavioral intention towards the technology (behavioral intention; participants: $M=3.94$,
292 $SD=0.87$; therapists: $M=4.24$, $SD=0.83$).

293 The top-3 advantages of Strolll for clinical implementation identified by the participants were: (1)
294 the ability to train at home, (2) its ability to promote increased physical activity, and (3) the enjoyable
295 nature of the training. Therapists identified the top-3 advantages, consistent before and after delivering the
296 Strolll intervention, as: (1) the enjoyable nature of the training, (2) its ability to promote increased
297 physical activity, and (3) the opportunity to monitor their patients remotely. The main barriers that
298 participants reported were: (1) technical issues (see Supplementary Material 6), (2) the need for sufficient

299 space at home, and (3) limited variation in exercises. Before the intervention, the top-3 disadvantages
 300 reported by therapists were (1) technical issues (see Supplementary Material 6), (2) reduced supervision,
 301 and in shared third place (3) unsuitability for every Parkinson's disease patient and financial costs. After
 302 delivering the intervention, the reported barriers shifted to (1) technical issues, (2) financial costs, and (3)
 303 the need for specific technical skills. These top-3 rankings were determined based on how frequently and
 304 prominently participants and therapists mentioned each factor (see Supplementary Material 7 for a
 305 comprehensive overview of reported advantages and disadvantages).

306

307 **Figure 4.** Visualization of the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) scores across the six subscales for
 308 participants (A) and therapists (B), relative to benchmark scores of the questionnaire. Error bars indicate
 309 the 95% confidence intervals.

Technology acceptance and use questionnaire

310

311 **Figure 5.** Technology acceptance and use questionnaire and the Strolll evaluation questionnaire for the 5-
312 point Likert-scale questions.

313

314 **3.3 Potential effectiveness**

315 A significant main effect of Time was observed for the LME analyses for all outcome measures (TUG,
316 Mini-BESTest, FTSTS, 10MWT at comfortable walking speed, and FES-I; all $p \leq 0.013$), except for the
317 10MWT at fast walking speed, showing a borderline significant effect of Time ($p = 0.053$), see Table. For
318 the primary outcome measure, TUG, and the 10MWT at fast walking speed, only the second reverse
319 Helmert contrast ($T2 - \text{mean}(T1, T0)$) was significant ($t(165.006) = -2.39, p = 0.018$ and $t(163.992) = -2.36,$
320 $p = 0.020$, respectively), indicating that improvements occurred only after the intervention. For the
321 secondary outcome measures Mini-BESTest, FTSTS, and 10MWT at comfortable walking speed,
322 significant improvements were observed after both the first ($T1 - T0$) and second reverse Helmert contrasts
323 ($T2 - \text{mean}(T1, T0)$); $p \leq 0.04$), indicating performance improvements after usual care, with further
324 improvement following the intervention. Regarding the FES-I, only the first reverse Helmert contrast
325 reached significance ($t(164.450) = 4.23, p < 0.001$), showing higher scores after the usual-care period
326 compared to baseline, suggesting an increased concern about falling following usual care only.

327

328 **Table.** Main effects of Time from the linear mixed-effects analyses with their reverse Helmert contrasts for the potential effectiveness
 329 concerning clinical test outcomes

	T0	T1	T2	Main effect of Time		1 st reverse Helmert contrast		2 nd reverse Helmert contrast			
	EMM	EMM	EMM	<i>F</i> (df)	<i>p</i>	<i>t</i> (df)	<i>p</i>	Δ T1-T0	<i>t</i> (df)	<i>p</i>	Δ T2-T1,T0
	(SE)	(SE)	(SE)					(SE)			(SE)
TUG (s)	8.56 (0.22)	8.30 (0.22)	8.09 (0.23)	<i>F</i> (2,163.59)=4.45	0.013	<i>t</i> (162.188)= -1.80	0.075	-0.27 (0.15)	<i>t</i> (165.006)= -2.39	0.018	-0.34 (0.14)
FTSTS (s)	13.79 (0.35)	12.73 (0.35)	11.99 (0.36)	<i>F</i> (2,164.09)=21.87	<0.001	<i>t</i> (162.431)= -4.15	<0.001	-1.06 (0.26)	<i>t</i> (165.763)= -5.17	<0.001	-1.27 (0.25)
10MWT comf (s)	8.23 (0.17)	7.99 (0.17)	7.74 (0.18)	<i>F</i> (2,163.27)=7.53	<0.001	<i>t</i> (161.885)= -2.07	0.040	-0.24 (0.12)	<i>t</i> (164.664)= -3.29	0.001	-0.36 (0.11)
10MWT fast (s)	6.42 (0.16)	6.36 (0.16)	6.18 (0.16)	<i>F</i> (2,163.00)=2.99	0.053	<i>t</i> (162.003)= -0.66	0.513	-0.06 (0.09)	<i>t</i> (163.992)= -2.36	0.020	-0.20 (0.09)
Mini- BESTest	23.09 (0.30)	23.80 (0.30)	24.41 (0.32)	<i>F</i> (2,164.56)=13.17	<0.001	<i>t</i> (162.418)= 3.01	0.003	0.72 (0.24)	<i>t</i> (166.714)= 4.16	<0.001	0.96 (0.23)
FES-I	24.20 (0.78)	26.67 (0.78)	25.70 (0.80)	<i>F</i> (2,165.44)=9.02	<0.001	<i>t</i> (164.450)= 4.23	<0.001	2.47 (0.59)	<i>t</i> (166.437)= 0.49	0.625	0.27 (0.54)

330 EMM = Estimated Marginal Means, SE = Standard error

331

332 **3.4 AR cues**

333 AR cues were deemed beneficial for 53 out of 92 participants. Participant characteristics (Hoehn & Yahr,
334 Freezers, MoCA score [cognitive dysfunctions], and baseline TUG) did not differ between participants
335 for whom AR cueing was and was not deemed beneficial (all $p>0.05$). The preferred type of cue varied
336 across participants: 2D lines (n=22), 3D obstacles (n=15), auditory rhythm (n=12), and dinosaur
337 footprints (n=4). Cue settings were personalized, resulting in a broad range of configurations
338 (Supplementary Material 8). Mentioned reasons for the decision to add AR cues to gamified exercises
339 were alleviating freezing of gait (n=6), improving step length (n=29), walking stability (n=15), foot
340 clearance (n=28), and other purposes (n=11), with multiple reasons possible per participant. These
341 findings support the hypothesis that most participants were deemed to benefit from adding AR cues and
342 that the selected type of cue and its settings varied among participants. As an example of an
343 individualized cueing approach, we highlight two participants: one participant preferred AR lines to
344 alleviate freezing and take big steps, with an intercue distance of 70 cm and a line width of 50 cm, while
345 another participant chose AR obstacles with an intercue distance of 66 cm and an obstacle height of 20 cm
346 to better lift the feet during walking. Eventually, 46 participants used personalized AR cues at home
347 during either Cue Challenge, Smash!, or both. Both participants and therapists generally found AR cues
348 valuable in Cue Challenge, while for Smash! their opinions varied (see Figure 5).

349 **4. Discussion**

350 This pragmatic clinical trial evaluated the clinical feasibility and potential effectiveness of Strolll, an AR
351 neurorehabilitation platform offering gamified gait-and-balance exercises for individuals with Parkinson's
352 disease, implemented in real-world clinical practice. Furthermore, the study explored the potential of
353 integrating personalized AR cueing into AR exercises.

354 **4.1 Feasibility**

355 This study was conducted under real-world conditions within clinical practice in the Netherlands, which
356 allowed us to evaluate Strolll beyond prior research-controlled conditions¹². Overall, the intervention
357 proved to be clinically feasible in terms of safety, adherence, performance, user experience, and
358 acceptability.

359 A large majority of participants (93.9%) started the independent home training with Strolll, nine
360 of whom withdrew for intervention-related reasons. No serious adverse events were reported during the
361 intervention period. A few participants reported symptoms associated with cyber sickness, like headache,
362 nausea, and dizziness (see Supplementary Material 5). Some of these symptoms may also have a different
363 origin than cyber sickness, such as exercise-induced dizziness through squatting or turning. Nevertheless,
364 prior research indicated that symptoms associated with cyber sickness can occur in augmented-reality
365 applications, but that their prevalence is generally lower than in virtual reality contexts^{30,31}, which seems
366 supported by the limited reports in the current study. Although two participants experienced a non-
367 injurious fall (out of >60.000 performed exercise minutes in total, one supervised in clinic and one
368 independent at home), the incidence rate was low relative to the study size, study duration, and nature of
369 the target population³². Furthermore, participants generally did not report fear of falling. This perception
370 supports the notion that the trajectory from in-clinic sessions to independent home-based exercise with
371 Strolll, under therapist prescription, is safe.

372 Therapists were able to prescribe, evaluate, and adjust the exercise program of the participants,
373 based on shared decision-making with the participants, throughout the intervention in terms of exercise
374 type (i.e., prescribed gamified exercises), duration (e.g., for a subset of participants [n=25] the prescribed
375 active-minutes was adjusted to align with their physical capacity), game-play level, and frequency. This
376 individualized approach presumably contributed to a high adherence compared to similar interventions
377 targeting individuals with Parkinson's disease³³, which was consistent with findings from our previous
378 research-led controlled study¹². This highlights the importance of individually tailoring prescribed
379 treatment programs in promoting long-term engagement and adherence and supports its feasibility when
380 implemented in the clinical pathway.

381 In terms of performance, Strolll was expected to be prescribed as a progressive but achievable
382 training. Participants demonstrated improvements over time, not only by executing higher game-play
383 levels but also by achieving higher game-play and functional performance scores. Notably, where our
384 prior research focused primarily on movement quantity scores (e.g., number of squats, meters walked)¹²,
385 performance scores were refined by tempo metrics (e.g., number of squats per minute, meters walked per
386 minute; see Figure 3 and Supplementary Material 2). As a result, we observed improvements not only in
387 game-play performance scores, but also in functional performance metrics (i.e., number of sit-to-
388 stands/squats, functional reaches, and meters walked per minute). These findings confirm the intended
389 progressive nature of Strolll, also when implemented in the clinical pathway.

390 The overall user experience was positive among both participants and therapists. UEQ results
391 revealed that across domains, Strolll was evaluated higher than the benchmarks, showing excellent ratings
392 for being able to offer a novel, attractive, and stimulating technology. A notable exception was the
393 (borderline) below-average rating for efficiency by therapists (see Figure 4), which may be due to being
394 relatively inexperienced in using this novel advanced form of rehabilitation technology and technical
395 inefficiencies (e.g., within the web portal for managing programs). The technology acceptance
396 questionnaire indicated a positive behavioral intention towards the use of Strolll, with the participants and

397 therapists demonstrating similar ratings across most subscales. Participants described the training as
398 enjoyable and appreciated the flexibility of being able to train at home and at their own convenience,
399 which is in line with our previous qualitative study³⁴. Therapists particularly valued the ability to monitor
400 their patients' progress remotely. Reported disadvantages included technical issues, which are not
401 uncommon in studies involving innovative digital interventions^{35,36}, limited training space at home (which
402 hindered the use of Wobbly Waiter and Cue Challenge), and perceived lack of variation in exercises.
403 These insights were shared with Strolll Limited for future optimization of the platform.

404 **4.2 Potential effectiveness**

405 The primary outcome measure, TUG, and the 10MWT at fast speed showed significant improvements
406 after the Strolll intervention. The other secondary outcome measures, including the Mini-BESTest,
407 FTSTS, and 10MWT at comfortable walking speed, showed significant improvements after usual care,
408 which limited the identification of subsequent intervention effects. Nevertheless, significant
409 improvements in those secondary clinical outcome measures were still observed after the Strolll
410 intervention. Although significant improvements in both primary and secondary outcome measures
411 following the intervention did not reach the minimal clinically important difference thresholds³⁷⁻⁴⁰ (i.e., no
412 clinically meaningful effect), they were consistently observed in the expected positive direction,
413 suggesting the potential effectiveness of Strolll in enhancing gait, balance, and fall-risk indicators. Thus,
414 although prior improvements after usual care may have attenuated effects, these improvements were
415 maintained and further enhanced, highlighting the potential added value of Strolll. Additionally,
416 participants and therapists also rated the perceived expectancy for improving gait and balance positively
417 (see Figure 5).

418 To conclusively validate the effectiveness of Strolll, a randomized controlled trial on clinical
419 outcomes is warranted⁴¹ and initiated⁴². Additionally, the effectiveness findings raise concerns about the
420 sensitivity of sparsely sampled clinical outcome measures (T0, T1, T2), due to ceiling or floor effects in
421 relatively high-functioning groups (e.g., M=8.53, SD=2.33 sec of TUG at baseline), and symptom

422 fluctuations common in Parkinson's disease. In that sense, the observed significant improvements in more
423 frequently sampled game-play and functional performance scores, such as increased walking distance per
424 minute, a higher number of sit-to-stands/squats per minute, and more functional reaches per minute
425 (Figure 3), suggest that Stroll targets aspects of gait and balance in a task-specific manner. However,
426 similar to most of the standard clinical outcome measures, these game-play and functional performance
427 scores primarily reflect aspects of movement quantity and tempo, while aspects of movement quality
428 remain less explored. The rich data captured by AR glasses offers a promising opportunity to align game-
429 play performance, functional performance, and movement-quality outcome measures more closely with
430 the task-specific rehabilitation goals of the gamified exercises, tentatively offering a greater
431 responsiveness to change than standard clinical assessments. Prior work has already demonstrated the
432 utility of AR data for valid and reliable parameterization of various gait and balance aspects during
433 standardized tests⁴³⁻⁴⁶. Accordingly, the potential of remotely collected gait-and-balance data during at-
434 home training will be further explored using the rich AR dataset of this trial (>60,000 minutes). At the
435 same time, further optimization between the gamified-exercise mechanics and their task-specific training
436 goals may strengthen the intended effects of the intervention, ultimately aiming to achieve an optimal
437 alignment among gamified-exercise mechanics (e.g., adding obstacles to Mole Patrol), task-specific
438 goals (e.g., including obstacle avoidance under walking adaptability), and their functional or movement-
439 quality outcome measures (e.g., obstacle-avoidance success rate).

440 **4.3 Integration of AR cueing**

441 AR cues were deemed beneficial for a slight majority of participants. Contrary to our expectations, these
442 participants did not differ from non-users in baseline characteristics. This may be due to the study's
443 broader focus on various gait impairments, rather than exclusively targeting freezing of gait. These
444 findings highlight the importance of personalized decision-making when integrating AR cueing into
445 rehabilitation exercises, rather than focusing on predefined subgroups such as individuals with freezing of

446 gait. Furthermore, both the type of cue and its settings varied over participants, supporting our expectation
447 that cueing is not a one-size-fits-all solution.

448 Some participants who initially opted to use AR cueing ultimately did not incorporate it into their
449 home training. This may have been due to either a lack of perceived benefits or practical barriers, such as
450 insufficient space at home to effectively apply spatial AR cues. For Smash!, some participants reported
451 that AR cues offered little or no added value, possibly because the exercise was already inherently goal-
452 directed (i.e., requiring participants to walk towards a pillar to punch an object from that pillar), making
453 the cues feel redundant or even distracting. However, exercises designed specifically for cueing, like Cue
454 Challenge and Wobbly Waiter, may hold promise for future research and clinical application for
455 improving aspects of gait, such as increasing step length, reducing shuffling, alleviating freezing of gait,
456 and improving gait speed in people with Parkinson's disease.

457 **4.4 Limitations and considerations**

458 The pragmatic nature of this study holds a potential bias regarding the potential effectiveness. Although
459 all participating therapists were trained prior to the study, assessments were conducted by different
460 clinicians at multiple sites, and minor deviations in clinical test execution cannot be excluded. This
461 variability could have affected both the validity and the inter-rater reliability of the measurements.
462 Nevertheless, this reflects the intended use of the platform in clinical practice, where such variability is
463 expected. Besides that, therapists had no prior experience with the use of AR technology in clinical
464 practice before this study. Increased familiarity with the technology may enhance their ability to
465 prescribe, evaluate, and adjust the intervention, individualized to the participant, which may optimize
466 clinical outcomes. In the current study, exercise prescription relied on therapists' clinical expertise in
467 combination with shared decision-making with participants and was potentially driven by adherence and
468 game scores available in the online web portal, where exercise prescription and its tailoring were
469 managed. Future implementation may benefit from more structured guidance (e.g., decision trees or
470 formats informed by baseline assessments of participants), which may support or guide individualization

471 of exercise prescription while reducing variability between therapists in exercise prescription.
472 Additionally, while the gait-and-balance assessments (T0, T1, and T2) were intended to be scheduled at
473 the same time of day for each participant, this could not be ensured in this pragmatic trial and may have
474 influenced potential effectiveness outcomes due to fluctuations in Parkinson's medication status. Another
475 important consideration is the heterogeneity of the participant population. Individuals differed not only in
476 clinical baseline characteristics and activity levels (see Supplementary Material 4) but also in how Strolll
477 was integrated into their regular therapy, always in addition to the in-clinic sessions, and possibly as a
478 replacement for their usual conventional home exercises. Whether participants actually performed such
479 prescribed conventional home exercises during usual care was not recorded in this study. Some
480 participants already demonstrated relatively high baseline scores on clinical outcome measures,
481 suggesting a more preserved functional status at the start of the intervention, while others were more
482 impaired. This heterogeneity, in combination with possible floor and ceiling effects in the clinical
483 outcome measures, may have influenced both the responsiveness to the intervention and the magnitude of
484 observed effects, and advocates for further personalization of the intervention and outcome measures
485 (e.g., task-specific outcome measures capturing the quality of movement).

486 **4.5 Implications for AR in clinical practice**

487 The findings of this study offer valuable insights for the future integration of AR technologies into
488 clinical practice. This study was implemented in the clinical pathway of the Dutch healthcare system,
489 where people with chronic neurological disorders such as Parkinson's disease are entitled to long-term,
490 all-year-round reimbursed therapy (after paying a limited out-of-pocket contribution). However, the
491 increasing pressure on the healthcare system, where there are not enough healthcare professionals
492 available to treat the increasing number of patients⁴⁷, calls for innovative solutions to ensure sustainable
493 and accessible care. Digital therapeutic solutions, like Strolll, which enable remotely prescribed, home-
494 based rehabilitation, align closely with the mission statement of care in the Netherlands⁴⁸: promoting care
495 at home, supporting independent care, and utilizing digital tools where possible. We showed that Strolll

496 feasibly contributes to this mission, where therapists considered the majority of their patients (93.9%)
497 eligible for independent, digitally supported therapy at home, potentially freeing up therapists' time to
498 focus more on patients with more complex needs (like the 6 participants in this study who were ineligible
499 for independent training at home, for example due to cognitive impairment). Earlier qualitative research
500 already suggested that people with Parkinson's disease are open to AR therapy at home, complementary
501 to physiotherapy³⁴. This is substantiated by the current study, which reflected positive behavioral
502 intentions towards AR therapy from both participants' and therapists' perspectives. Such home-based
503 therapies are needed to alleviate the burden on the healthcare system while enhancing accessibility and
504 continuity of care. Future studies should incorporate health-technology assessments (HTA) and cost-
505 effectiveness analyses to further evaluate the feasibility of Stroll into clinical practice. Additionally,
506 alternative models for AR rehabilitation, other than the home-based model presented here, should be
507 explored, such as independent or lightly supervised in-clinic use and small-group training.

508 Our findings also indicate that the intended use and users of Stroll could be broadened. Beyond
509 its focus on gait, balance, and fall risk, the platform may play a valuable role in promoting increased
510 physical activity through engaging, immersive home-based rehabilitation exercises performed at the
511 user's own convenience. Promoting increased physical activity is particularly relevant given the
512 commonly low(er) activity levels in people with Parkinson's disease⁴⁹, which are associated with negative
513 health outcomes^{50,51}. Growing evidence suggests that exercise at an adequate intensity level may have
514 disease-modifying effects by positively influencing neurobiological processes such as neural growth,
515 inflammation, and brain connectivity⁵², thereby highlighting the value of integrating physical activity into
516 routine care for this population⁵³. In this context, the potential of Stroll to promote greater activity levels
517 is noteworthy, which was also identified in the current study by participants and therapists, explicitly
518 mentioning it in their top-3 advantages, as well as in prior qualitative research with this type of AR
519 therapy³⁴.

520 **5. Conclusion**

521 This pragmatic clinical trial demonstrates that Strolll, when implemented in a real-world setting, is safe,
522 adherable, progressive, user-friendly, and well-accepted by both individuals with Parkinson’s disease and
523 their therapists. Strolll showed potential to improve gait, balance, and fall-risk indicators, although the
524 observed effects did not exceed minimal clinically important differences. Findings on the integration of
525 AR cueing highlight the importance of taking an individualized approach. Future development may
526 position Strolll not only as a physical therapy tool for remotely managed independent gait-and-balance
527 rehabilitation, but also as a technology-driven solution to promote physical activity and improve
528 accessibility of care.

529 **Data availability**

530 The authors confirm that the data supporting the findings of this study are available within the article and
531 its Supplementary Material 10.

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536 **Clinical Trial Registration**

537 This study was registered at ClinicalTrials.gov (NCT06590987)

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543

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544 **Ethics approval**

545 Ethical approval was obtained from the accredited Medical Ethics Committee United, the Netherlands
546 (R24.008, NL86191.100.24). Participants signed their individual informed consent prior to participating
547 in the study, in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

548 **Conflict of interest**

549 MR is a scientific advisor with share options for Strolll Ltd., a digital therapeutics company building AR
550 software for physical rehabilitation, for one day a week in addition to his main positions as associate
551 professor Technology in Motion at Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam and Senior Scientist at Maastricht
552 University. The remaining authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any
553 commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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